

A copro-antigen ELISA for the detection of ascarid infections in chickens

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ABSTRACT

A reliable method of diagnosing the most prevalent helminth infections in chickens is vital for developing effective control strategies. *Ascaridia galli* and *Heterakis gallinarum* are phylogenetically close nematode species that can elicit the development of cross-reactive antibodies in chickens. Therefore, an enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) based on *Ascaridia galli* antigens in faeces of chickens to detect and quantify infections with both *A. galli* and *H. gallinarum* was developed. The ELISA utilised polyclonal antibodies that were obtained from rabbits immunised with soluble antigens isolated from *A. galli*. In two separate experiments, chickens were kept as uninfected controls or were orally infected with either 100 or 1000 of embryonated eggs of *A. galli* or *H. gallinarum*. Faecal samples were collected after 28–30 weeks post-infection. The ELISA was then used to quantify the concentration of soluble worm antigens in faecal samples, i.e., the amount of antigen per gram faeces, APG. The APG from infected chickens was significantly higher than non-infected groups in both experiments (P 0.001). Both 100 and 1000 infection dose groups were not significantly different (P = 0.999) in the experiment with *H. gallinarum*, whereas in the experiment with *A. galli*, APG was significantly higher in the 1000 infection group (P 0.001). A receiver operation characteristics (ROC) analysis that evaluates the qualitative performance of diagnostic tests was used to calculate the assay parameters within each mono-infection experiment. The result showed that the assay had a high diagnostics accuracy with an area-under-curve (AUC) of 0.99 in detecting infection in *A. galli* infected chickens and a moderate-high accuracy (AUC = 0.89) in birds infected with *H. gallinarum*. The diagnostic sensitivity and specificity of the assay at the optimal cut-off point equivalent to Youden index were 93% and 100% for detecting infections in *A. galli* experiment and 85% and 92% in *H. gallinarum* experiment, respectively. The correlation between faecal antigen concentration and all worm burden parameters was positive but generally low ($r < 0.33$), which provided less information about infection intensities. Nonetheless, these results indicate that a reliable and accurate qualitative diagnosis of the two most prevalent intestinal nematodes in chickens can be achieved using a non-invasive copro-antigen ELISA assay.

1. Introduction

Ascaridia galli and *Heterakis gallinarum* are two economically important gastrointestinal nematode species that are common globally (Thapa et al., 2015; Shifaw et al., 2021). They are more widespread than other common helminths of chicken like *Capillaria spp.* and *Raillietina spp.* (Shifaw et al., 2021). These species have pathogenic effects that are associated with damage to intestinal tissue, reduced nutrient absorption and utilisation and impaired growth and laying performance (Dahl et al., 2002; Daş et al., 2011, 2012; Sharma et al., 2019; Stehr et al., 2019). Consequences of infection, especially the level of mortality have been shown to be associated with infection level (Hinrichsen et al., 2016).

The gold standard technique for examining the severity of nematode infections is to directly count the number of worms present in the intestine of the infected host post-mortem (Permin & Hansen, 1998). As this method requires necropsy, microscopic counting of parasite eggs in host faeces has been the classical method of indicating the presence and severity of infections (Nielsen, 2021).

Although, faecal egg counts (FEC) indeed had moderate to strong correlations with worm burdens in chickens (Thapa et al., 2015; Daş et al., 2017; Sharma et al., 2018; Feyerera et al., 2022) the results are not consistent and not always reliable for several reasons. Egg shedding through faeces can only occur if infected hosts harbour matured female worms, whereas immature stages and male worms do not (at least

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directly) contribute to the egg shedding. The uneven distribution of eggs in host faeces, diurnal fluctuations in eggs shed, predilection site of the parasite species in the gastrointestinal tract and variation in worms' fecundity can also impede the reliability of egg counts for diagnosing infection (Wongrak et al., 2015; Daş et al., 2019).

The efforts to find an alternative reliable method to FEC led to the development of an enzymatic linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) that measures anti-ascarid antibody in plasma and egg-yolks of infected hosts (Daş et al., 2017; Sharma et al., 2018). While the assay provided a better qualitative diagnosis than FEC, it was not a better tool to determine the severity of infections. Moreover, plasma antibody ELISA requires both an authorised field expert and an invasive technique to obtain the blood samples, while egg yolk antibody ELISA can only be performed for matured female chickens, leaving male and young chickens out of the scope. Hence, a non-invasive alternative to FEC that can capture all groups of birds and different developmental stages of worms is still missing.

An ELISA that quantifies the concentration of parasite antigens in hosts' faeces (copro-antigens) is a non-invasive method that could also be used for evaluating the infection status of the living host given the presence of excretory/secretory products of parasites in the host intestine (Allan & Craig, 2006). Copro-antigens have been used in the evaluation of parasitic infections with considerably higher accuracy than FEC in cattle, sheep, pigs, red deer, horses, and dogs (Palmer et al., 2014; Kajugu et al., 2015; French et al., 2016; Martínez-Sernández et al., 2016; Lagatie et al., 2020), but its' performance in diagnosing chickens infected with either *A. galli* or *H. gallinarum* has not been reported.

Given that chickens develop cross-reactive antibodies (Daş et al., 2017) to these two phylogenetically close nematode species (Nadler et al., 2007; Wang et al., 2016), a copro-antigen ELISA coated with a specific antibody against one species could be sensitive to antigens of other related species. Therefore, this study was designed with three objectives *i*) to evaluate the potential of an ELISA to capture worm antigens in host faeces and to discriminate between nematode infected chickens and non-infected ones *ii*) to test whether an ELISA that uses anti-*A. galli* polyclonal antibody could also measure antigens of *H. gallinarum* in host faeces and *iii*) to evaluate if copro-antigen ELISA would provide adequate information about infection intensities.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Sample description

This study utilised faecal samples collected from two independent nematode infection experiments in which laying hens (Lohmann Selected Leghorn, LSL) were infected with different doses of embryonated eggs of either *A. galli* or *H. gallinarum* and were left infected for a long period to allow reinfections with the same species. The aim of the experiments from which data were collected was to evaluate the diagnostic accuracy of ELISA using plasma and egg yolk samples in comparison with faecal egg count (FEC), hence, the data for worm burden, antibody response and the faecal egg counts from these two independent experiments have been previously published (Daş et al., 2017; 2018). However, the analysis of copro-antigen using samples from these experiments has not been reported and is the core idea newly presented in this study. Readers are therefore referred to previously published articles for details about the experimental animals and infection procedures (Daş et al., 2017; 2018). Briefly, in each experiment, the LSL chickens were divided into three groups. One group was kept as uninfected control, and the birds of the other two groups were either experimentally infected with 100 or 1000 embryonated/infective eggs of either nematode species. The birds used in this experiment were purchased from commercial hatchery at one-day of age and reared under strict conditions free of helminth. The birds were reared in a floor husbandry system with wood shavings as the litter material and were fed commercial diets *ad libitum*. The birds were 16 and 4 weeks old at the time of

infection in *A. galli* and *H. gallinarum* experiments, respectively. Analysis of pooled faecal samples on infection day showed no gastrointestinal helminth infection during the pre-experimental period. The infection-free status of the birds at the beginning of the experiment was also confirmed by assessing plasma anti-ascarid antibody levels (Daş et al., 2018). Approval for experimental infection was provided by the ethics committee of the Lower Saxony State Office for Consumer Protection and Food Safety, Germany (Permission no: AZ:33.9-42502-04-12/0707). Post-mortem parasitological examination was done at 28 and 30-weeks post-infection (wpi) in *A. galli* and *H. gallinarum*, respectively, according to the recommended practice for experimental infections of chickens (Yazwinski et al., 2003). Worms were classified as either larvae or matured worms based on general morphology as reported in a previous study (Daş et al., 2017). The average length of the worms was estimated by measuring 20 randomly selected worms (10 worms per sex) in each bird at necropsy. Prior to post-mortem evaluation, the birds were transferred to individual cages for 24 h to collect daily total faeces, which included both intestinal droppings and the caecal excreta. The daily total faeces were homogenized thoroughly and stored at -20°C . The number of faecal samples used to determine antigen concentration in both experiments is shown in Table 1.

2.2. Preparation of the copro-ELISA for the detection of ascarids antigen in host's faeces

2.2.1. Antigen isolation from *A. galli*

To isolate soluble antigens from worms, thawed intact worms were initially washed thrice with phosphate-buffered saline (PBS), followed by one wash with 70% ethanol and lastly with another PBS wash. Homogenisation of the worms was done in a mortar after which one part of the worm was extracted using two parts of a basic buffer containing 35 mM BisTris, 25 mM Tris, pH 9 for 5 min. This was then followed by centrifugation at 17,000, 4°C for 15 min. The supernatant representing the soluble antigen was collected and used as standard.

2.2.1.1. Rabbit immunisation. The soluble antigen was used for immunization of a rabbit. For this, the rabbit was immunized three times at 2 weeks interval with 25 μl of antigen (soluble worm extract), 175 μl PBS, and 200 μl Montanide adjuvant ISA 206 (immunoGlobe Antikörpertechnik GmbH, Himmelstadt, Germany). After initial test bleeding of ~ 5 ml serum, additional booster was given. The rabbit was exsanguinated (min. 35–45 ml serum) after three times of large bleeding (~ 15 ml serum) at two weeks interval. Permission for immunization of the rabbit was obtained from the relevant state authority ('Government of Lower Franconia', AZ 55.2-2531.01-57/11).

2.2.2. Faecal sample preparation

A total of 50 mg of the homogenized, defrosted faeces from each individual chicken was weighed and ten parts of sample buffer (0.12 M NaCl, 0.02 M Na₂HPO₄, 0.01 M EDTA, 0.2% BSA, 0.1% gelatine hydrolysate, 0.05% Tween 20) was added to 1 part of each of the weighed faecal samples. The mixture was intensively vortexed and left to settle for 10–20 min. The supernatant (100 μl) was collected and pipetted into the assay wells.

2.2.3. ELISA procedures

A 96-well microtiter plate (Costar 2592, Corning, USA) was used for the sandwich ELISA.

The plates were coated with 100 μl of anti-Ascaridia polyclonal rabbit antibody at a concentration of 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ in coating buffer (0.05 M NaHCO₃; pH 9.6). Antibodies were purified by using Protein A Sepharose Fast Flow according to the protocol specified by the manufacturer (Cytiva, USA). After overnight incubation at 4°C , the wells were blocked with washing buffer (10% PBS, 0.05% Tween 20) for 1 h and

Table 1Mean, median and range of worm counts, EPG and APG in both *Ascaridia galli* and *Heterakis gallinarum* experiments.

Experiment		Experimental Group								
		0-dose			100-dose			1000-dose		
		Mean	Median	Range	Mean	Median	Range	Mean	Median	Range
<i>A. galli</i>	Larvae (n/ bird)	0	0	0	2.9 ^a	2.0	11.0	10.5 ^b	5.0	79.0
	Mature (n/ bird)	0	0	0	34.2 ^a	29.0	105.0	39.4 ^a	28.0	114.0
	Total (n/ bird)	0	0	0	37.1 ^a	34.0	109.0	49.8 ^a	45.0	114.0
	EPG	0	0	0	526.5 ^a	200.0	3250.0	1802.8 ^a	450.0	15900.0
	APG (µg/g faeces)	0.02 ^a	0.02	0.03	0.12 ^b	0.09	0.28	0.32 ^c	0.17	1.82
<i>H. gallinarum</i>	Larvae (n/ bird)	0	0	0	85.4 ^a	62.0	262.0	82.7 ^a	64.0	420.0
	Mature (n/ bird)	0	0	0	410.2 ^a	386.0	970.0	453.5 ^a	418.0	1086.0
	Total (n/ bird)	0	0	0	495.6 ^a	440.0	1134.0	536.2 ^a	482.0	1309.0
	EPG	0	0	0	472.8 ^a	349.0	2351.0	334.7 ^a	199.0	1650.0
	APG (µg/g faeces)	0.05 ^a	0.04	0.11	0.10 ^b	0.10	0.14	0.12 ^b	0.09	0.97

Means in the same row with different superscript are significantly different ($P < 0.05$). Statistical analyses of the data are based on analysis of variance using log transformed data ($\text{Log}(y + 1)$). Whereas means, median and range presented are based on untransformed data. $n = 41$ in 100 dose group in both experiments and $n = 31$ in 1000 dose group in *A. galli* experiment and 41 in 1000 dose group in *H. gallinarum* experiment. Number of samples in 0 dose group is 9 and 25 in *A. galli* and *H. gallinarum* experiments, respectively. Note that 0-dose group was excluded from the statistical comparisons with 100 and 1000 dose groups for worm burden and EPG data.

then washed five times with 350 µl washing buffer. Plates were stabilised by using 300 µl of 20% sucrose solution for 1 h. After decantation, the plates were dried at room temperature for 3–4 days and stored with silica gel at 4 °C until use.

Initial run of the ELISA was done multiple times (up to 30x) to establish optimal antibody and biotin conjugate concentrations, and to determine optimal buffer and assay conditions. For the first step after optimisation, 10 µl of chicken serum from non-infected animals were pipetted in each well to saturate the polyclonal antibodies and reduce the unspecific binding by exclusion of these antibodies. 100 µl standards of 400, 200, 100, 50, 25, and 0 ng soluble antigen/ml were added to the assay wells in duplicate while controls and infected samples were in single determination. The assay was then incubated at room temperature (20 – 25 °C) for 4 h on a microplate shaker (500 rpm).

After incubation, the plate was washed three times with 350 µl of washing buffer (10% PBS; 0.05% Tween 20) before adding a biotinylated anti-*Ascaridia* polyclonal rabbit antibody (TECODevelopment, GmbH, Germany). The antibody (Protein A purified) was conjugated to Biotinamidohexanoic acid Nhydroxysuccinimide ester (Sigma). The biotin-antibody conjugate was diluted in biotinylated antibody buffer (70 ng/ml in sample diluent containing 5% normal rabbit serum and 0.5% casein). To each well, 100 µl of diluted biotin antibody conjugate was added, followed by 30 min incubation at room temperature on a shaker (500 rpm). After three washing steps with 350 µl of diluted washing buffer, 100 µl of enzyme conjugate (Streptavidin-PolyHRP20 conjugate, SDT, Baesweiler, Germany) at 200 ng/ml in PBS containing 0.05% Tween 20 was incubated for 30 mins on a plate shaker. After an additional 5 washes, the TMB substrate (TMBS, SurModics, MN, USA) was added for and left for 30 min on a plate shaker, followed by termination with 100 µl of 1 M hydrochloric acid and an OD measurement at 450 nm with a 650 nm reference filter using an Emax Plus Microplate reader (Molecular Devices, USA) with software SoftMax Pro 6.5.1 (Molecular Devices, USA). The conversion of OD to concentration (in ng/ml) via the standard curve was done using a 4-parameter logistic (4-PL) curve-fit of the SoftMax Pro software (Molecular Device, USA). The equation for the 4-PL model is:

$$y = \frac{a - d}{1 + \left(\frac{x}{c}\right)^b} + d$$

Where; y = the measured OD.

x = the concentration.

a = the minimum value.

d = the maximum value.

c = point of inflection.

b = slope of the curve.

Antigen concentration in faeces was then estimated as the amount of ascarid antigen per gram of faeces (APG, µg/g faeces) based on the standard curve for 400, 200, 100, 50, 25, 0 ng soluble antigen/ml. The assay read out (ng/ml) was multiplied by our dilution factor of 11 (as 10 parts of buffer was added to 1 part of weighed faeces) and results were further converted to µg/g.

The intra- and inter-assay coefficient of variation (CV) for this assay were 5.7% and 5.3% respectively. The CV determination was based on three independent assays performed with 5 random samples in 5 duplicates.

2.2.4. Faecal egg counts

A random fresh sub-sample (4 g) was obtained from thoroughly mixed daily faeces and analysed with the McMaster egg counting technique (MAFF, 1986). A saturated NaCl solution (specific gravity = 1.2) was used as the flotation liquid and minimum detection level of egg counting technique was set to 50 eggs per gram faeces (EPG).

2.3. Statistical analysis

Statistical analyses of total worm count, larva counts and APG data were based on log transformation of the data to correct for heterogeneity of variance and to produce approximately normally distributed data. Transformation was done using a natural logarithm function [$\text{Ln}(y) = \ln(y + 1)$]. Differences in APG and worm burden between infection-dose groups within each experiment were analysed with one-way ANOVA using the function in the R programme (R Core Team, 2021).

Furthermore, a receiver operation characteristics (ROC) analysis was performed to assess the diagnostic accuracy of the copro-antigen ELISA using APG data. The ROC analysis is a commonly used method valid for evaluating the qualitative performance of a diagnostic test (Nielsen, 2021). The ROC calculates the area-under-the-curve (AUC), non-arbitrary threshold value, diagnostic sensitivity, and specificity of the assay (Swets, 1988). The ROC curve is a plot of the true positive rate in function of the false positive rate for all possible cut-off points. The AUC is an overall summary of the ROC curve across all cut-off points, and it indicates the probability of discriminating between infected and uninfected populations.

The ROC analysis was done using the pROC package in R programming software (Robin et al., 2011) for each mono-infection experiment, separately. For the analysis, samples from birds that harbour worms (i.e. gold standard) in both initial-infection dose groups in each experiment were considered an infected case (i.e., positive case) while the control birds (all free of worms) were classified as control case (i.e., negative

case). In the 'roc' function of the software, infection status (i.e., control vs infected) were set as the response, while the assay outcome (APG data) was set as the predictor. The function sets a cut-off as the mean of two consecutive values in the APG data. At each of these cut-offs, the diagnostic sensitivity was estimated as the true positive/(true positive + false negatives) value while diagnostic specificity was calculated as true negative/(true negatives + false positive) value. It is important to note that the test specificity here implies a differentiation between infected and uninfected birds and not differentiation between the two parasites as we examined birds from two independent mono-species infections with their own uninfected-control counterparts. The minimum sample size required for a valid ROC analysis was calculated using Medcalc statistical software version 20.023 (MedCalc, 2020) with a pre-set significance level of 0.05, maximum AUC of 0.99 and group ratio of 1. The optimal values for diagnostic sensitivity and specificity were selected according to the criteria value corresponding to the Youden index (J) (Youden, 1950; Ruopp et al., 2008). This represent the cut-off point where the difference between the true positive rates and false positive rate is at maximum. The ROC curve showing plots of diagnostic sensitivity and specificity values at all cut off point was generated, and the AUC was estimated.

Test accuracy of the assays was interpreted based on the range of the AUC value and are classified as follows; low accuracy ($0.5 < \text{AUC} \leq 0.7$), moderate accuracy ($0.7 < \text{AUC} \leq 0.9$) or high accuracy ($\text{AUC} > 0.90$) (Hanley and McNeil, 1982).

The correlation between APG and worm burden parameters (total worm burden, total worm length, total larva count) was estimated by Pearson correlation analysis using R software. Analysis was based on log-transformed data except for total worm length. Total worm length was calculated by multiplying the average worm length by the number of worms and was done separately for each worm sex. The raw data used for all analyses in this study are stored in a repository (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.705607](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.705607)).

3. Results

3.1. Effects of mono-species infections and infection dose on copro-antigen concentration

The overall fixed effect of infection on APG was significant ($P < 0.001$) in both *A. galli* (Fig. 1) and *H. gallinarum* (Fig. 2) experiments. APG was also significantly different between the two infection doses in chickens that were infected with *A. galli*. Groups infected with 1000 *A.*

galli eggs had a significantly ($P < 0.001$) higher concentration of APG than birds infected with only 100 eggs. Whereas, in the experiment with *H. gallinarum* infected birds, APG concentration was not significantly different ($P = 0.937$) between the two infection doses.

3.2. Effects of initial-infection dose on the worm burden

All but one of the experimentally infected birds harboured worms at the end of the experimental period. As confirmed through parasitological examination of the intestines and FEC, uninfected control birds remained nematode-free until the end of respective experiments. As shown in Table 1, the effect of the initial infection dose was not significant ($P > 0.05$) on the total worm burden in both experiments where birds were initially infected either with *A. galli* or *H. gallinarum* and then exposed to re-infection with the same species. In addition, larva count did not differ significantly between the two infection doses ($P = 0.850$) in chickens infected with *H. gallinarum*, however, it was significantly higher ($P = 0.004$) in chickens infected with 1000 instead of 100 *A. galli* eggs.

Fig. 1. Ascarid-antigen concentrations per gram faeces of chickens in *Ascaridia galli* experiment ($n = 81$). Birds were either kept as uninfected (●) or infected (●) with 100 or 1000 eggs of *A. galli*. Necropsy was performed at 28 weeks post-infection to examine worm burden and faecal samples collected to measure antigen concentration. Dots above the dashed line ($\geq 5.0 \mu\text{g} / \text{g}$) are shown on an extended reduced scale [reduced y-axis = $(y * 0.01 + 5)$] to depict a focused picture of the whole data. The figure represents raw data, but the statistical comparisons are based on the log-transformed data.

Fig. 2. Ascarid-antigen concentrations per gram faeces of chickens in *Heterakis gallinarum* experiment ($n = 107$). Birds were either kept as uninfected (●) or infected (●) with 100 or 1000 eggs of *H. gallinarum*. Faecal samples to measure antigen concentration were collected at 30 weeks post infection when birds were slaughtered for parasitological examination. Dots above the dashed line ($\geq 5.0 \mu\text{g} / \text{g}$) are shown on an extended reduced scale [reduced y-axis = $(y * 0.01 + 5)$] to depict a focused picture of the whole data. The figure represents raw data, but the statistical comparisons are based on the log-transformed data.

Fig. 3. Plots of correlation coefficients of faecal antigen concentration (APG) and faecal egg count (FEC) with worm burden parameters in *Ascaridia galli* experiment (a) and *Heterakis gallinarum* experiment (b).

Tot_FL: Total Female worm Length; Tot_LE: Total worm length; Tot_ML: Total male worm length. MatureCount: Total number of adult worm count; LarvaCount: Total larvae count; FEC: Faecal egg count; APG: Antigen concentration per gram faeces.

3.3. Correlation between APG and worm burden

All correlations are presented in Fig. 3. The correlation (r) between APG and all worm burden parameters in each experiment was positive albeit with generally low coefficients ($r < 0.33$). For example, in chickens infected with *A. galli*, the correlation between APG and total worm burden yielded a coefficient (r) of 0.28 that was nevertheless significantly different from zero ($P < 0.050$). A higher correlation coefficient was calculated between APG and total length of male worms ($r = 0.33$, $P < 0.050$) than length of female worms ($r = 0.23$, $P = 0.381$). None of the correlations of APG with the respective worm burden parameters was significant in *H. gallinarum* infected animals ($P > 0.05$). APG was positively correlated with EPG ($r = 0.37$, $P < 0.05$) in *A. galli* experiment. EPG had considerably higher correlation coefficient ($r \geq 0.47$) with worm burden parameters compared to APG in *A. galli* experiment. In this experiment, correlation between FEC with total worm count had coefficient of $r = 0.56$, while it was $r = 0.62$ for EPG and counts of mature *A. galli* worms.

3.4. Qualitative diagnostic performance of the copro-antigen ELISA assay

We applied a ROC analysis to investigate the qualitative performance of the ELISA for quantifying APG. As shown in Figs. 4 and 5, the results showed that the assay had a high overall diagnostic accuracy (AUC = 0.99) when used to identify chickens that were infected with *A. galli*. In chickens infected with *H. gallinarum*, the diagnostic accuracy of the assay was moderately high (AUC = 0.89). The assay could identify all

truly negative chickens in the *A. galli* experiment with 100% diagnostic specificity while in the *H. gallinarum* experiment, the assay falsely classified 8% of the uninfected chickens at the optimal cut-off value (Fig. 5b). The diagnostic sensitivity of the assay was 93% for detecting infections in *A. galli* experiment and 85% for detecting infection in *H. gallinarum* experiment. In addition, the assay had a negative predictive value (npv) of 90% and a positive predictive value (ppv) of 100% in detecting infections in *A. galli* experiment whereas in *H. gallinarum* experiment, the assay had npv of 65%. and ppv of 97%.

Due to the lack of significant differences in the total worm burdens of the birds between the two initial infection dose groups (i.e., 100 vs. 1000 eggs) in either infection experiment, we pooled APG data of all birds that harboured worms from both dose groups as an infected case (i.e., positive case) for the analysis. However, we present the diagnostics performance of the assay for each infection dose separately in the Supplementary Figure 1. In the experiment with *A. galli* the ELISA test had AUC of 0.98 for the 100-dose group and 0.99 in 1000-dose group. The AUC for the ELISA was 0.88 for both 100 and 1000 infection group in the *H. gallinarum* experiment.

4. Discussion

This is the first study to provide insight into the use of worm antigens in host faeces to detect and quantify ascarids infections in chickens. For this, we developed a copro-antigen ELISA that accurately differentiated between non-infected chickens, and chickens infected either with *A. galli* or *H. gallinarum* at different doses. A differentiation between *A. galli* and

Fig. 4. A). ROC curve based on known infection status of chickens (n = 76) in *Ascaridia galli* experiment. The diagonal line corresponds to the half of the maximum area under curve (i.e., AUC = 1.0). The farther the location of the ROC curve is from the diagonal line, the higher the total test accuracy analyses. B). A logistic plot of the binary infection status (1 = infected, 0 = control) with continuous predictor, APG. Vertical dotted line shows the optimal cut-off point representing Youden Index.

Fig. 5. A). ROC curve based on known infection status of chickens ($n = 105$) in *Heterakis gallinarum* experiment. The diagonal line corresponds to the half of the maximum area under curve (i.e., $AUC = 1.0$). The farther the location of the ROC curve is from the diagonal line, the higher the total test accuracy analyses. B). A logistic plot of the binary infection status ($1 =$ infected, $0 =$ control) with continuous predictor, APG. Vertical dotted line shows the optimal cut-off point representing Youden Index.

H. gallinarum infected chickens was however not tested. Given the significant difference in APG between infected and non-infected groups obtained in this study, we conclude that measurement of worm antigens present in host faeces allows our method to distinguish (Figs. 1 and 2) noninfected birds from birds infected with either nematode species. We could, however, not find any linear relationship between infection dose and severity of infection at the end of our experiment, likely because of reinfections that eliminate impact of primary infections (Das et al., 2018). In addition, dose-dependency in establishment rate of the nematodes might have led to similar worm burdens as earlier reported by (Permin et al., 1997), where infection with 100, 500 or 2500 eggs of *A. galli* had no significant effect on the worm burden after 8 wpi. In contrast to these findings, Feyera and colleagues (2022) showed evidence of a significant difference in worm burdens between chicks infected with low dose (100) and high (900) of *A. galli* eggs (Feyera et al., 2022). The authors reported that there was a minimal possibility for re-infection by wpi 8–10 when necropsy was done. Whereas, in the current study, the parasitological examination was done at 28–30 wpi—enough time for reinfection to occur as it would in a natural condition. Previous research suggests that the majority of worms from initial experimental infection are expelled up to 31- and 36-days post-infection for both *A. galli* and *H. gallinarum* respectively (Stehr et al., 2018). Thus, most of the worms found in the birds at 28–30 wpi must have resulted from naturally occurring re-infections, which might have eliminated the effect of the initial infection dose on worm burden in the current study. This offers the possibility of comparing our test in a similar situation as in natural infection conditions.

It is important to note that even though there was no effect of infection dose on total worm burden, the 1000-dose group had higher larvae count in *A. galli* infected birds.

Similarly, this group had significantly higher antigen concentrations than the 100-dose group. This might suggest that the higher larvae count may have contributed to the higher antigen concentration obtained for the 1000-dose group suggesting that antigens could already be captured in faeces of the hosts containing only immature worms. This assumption could however not be confirmed in the present study as there was no significant correlation between faecal antigen concentration and larvae counts. An earlier report suggested that copro-antigen can be measured in dogs infected with *Echinococcus granulosus* and *Taenia pisiformis* weeks

prior to patency and are independent of egg output (Allan & Craig, 2006). This present study did not, however, evaluate the detection of ascarids antigen prior to patency as faecal samples for APG analyses were available only at the end of the experiment. Thus, further studies are encouraged to quantify worm antigens in chicken faeces before patency and during infection.

We had previously provided the evidence that chickens develop cross-reactive antibodies (Daş et al., 2017) against the two closely related nematode species used in this study (Nadler et al., 2007; Wang et al., 2016), which allows for the use of one assay to diagnose two different nematode species without separation between the two infections. Therefore, in the present study, we used soluble antigens of *A. galli* as standards in a sandwich ELISA coated with anti-ascarid polyclonal rabbit antibody to quantify antigen concentration in the faeces of both *A. galli* and *H. gallinarum* infected chickens. Such an assay would be useful in the field where both nematode species are known to co-infect chickens, and mono-infection rarely occurs (Kaufmann et al., 2011; Thapa et al., 2015). The evaluation of the assay showed a high diagnostic accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity in *A. galli* infected chickens (Figs. 4 and 5) while, the assay showed slightly lower diagnostic specificity and sensitivity for detecting infection in *H. gallinarum*. This limitation, at least for experimental purposes, could be overcome with further improvement to the assay especially by limiting variability in the proteins targeted. This can be achieved by exploring more specific worm proteins that could yield a better sensitivity/specificity profile for each of the two worm species.

Until now, no published report on the use and accuracy of a copro-antigen ELISA assay in detecting *A. galli* and *H. gallinarum* infection in poultry is available, although its use is widely explored in other species. For example, Jara and colleagues reported a high accuracy ($AUC = 0.995$)—comparable to our result—for a copro-antigen ELISA in the detection of *E. granulosus* soluble antigens in dogs, where they used an anti-*E. granulosus* polyclonal rabbit antibody (Jara et al., 2019). They reported a higher diagnostic sensitivity and specificity of 96.5% and 98% respectively than what was obtained in this study. Similarly, a copro-antigen ELISA which measured a specific ABA-1 *Ascaris lumbricoides* antigen was used to detect ascarids infection in pigs and humans (Lagatie et al., 2020). The assay had a specificity of 95.3% and sensitivity of 91.5% which is also similar to what we found in the current

study. Our results are therefore within the range of other established methods used for other species.

Another objective of this study was to assess the performance of copro-antigen ELISA in indicating intensity of infection. We found positive but low correlations between APG and total worm burdens in both experiments. Our data were obtained from a single necropsy time point wpi 28/30 which does not allow to capture solely larvae antigens given that the majority of larvae expelled in a few weeks (Stehr et al., 2018).

Generally, a copro-antigen test has several advantages over classical parasitological diagnostics methods (i.e., FEC). FEC has been used as the standard proxy for adult female worm burden and infection intensity (Sharma et al., 2019; Nielsen, 2021) and it is known to correlate significantly with worm burden, especially for *A. galli* (Thapa et al., 2015; Daş et al., 2017; Feyera et al., 2022). However, FEC is prone to false negatives and does not correctly represent the dynamics of worms as worm eggs are only shed by matured female worms. By contrast, copro-antigen ELISA is not dependent on the presence of eggs or worm sex (Allan & Craig, 2006; Elsemore et al., 2014). Furthermore, worm antigens in host faeces are quite stable for days at temperatures ranging from – 80–35 °C (Allan & Craig, 2006).

5. Conclusion

A single non-invasive copro-antigen ELISA for the detection and quantification of infection in chickens infected with either *A. galli* or *H. gallinarum* was developed. Taken together, the findings suggest that a copro-antigen ELISA can reliably detect infections with either species of nematode studied. But the correlation between the antigen concentration in faeces and actual worm burden is rather low and further improvement would be required to evaluate the use of copro-antigen ELISA to quantify infection intensities.

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CRediT authorship contribution statement

Oyekunle John Oladosu: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Writing – original draft. **Mark Hennies:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **Matthias Gauly:** Conceptualization, Funding, Writing – review & editing. **Gürbüz Daş:** Conceptualization, Funding, Project administration, Investigation, Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

Conflict of interest

The authors have read the journal's policy and have the following competing interests: MH is an employee of TECODevelopment GmbH. This does not alter our adherence to Veterinary Parasitology policies on sharing data and materials. There is no patent associated with this research to declare. Other authors have no competing interest.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at doi:10.1016/j.vetpar.2022.109795.

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